

THE INFLUENCE OF THE FINANCIAL-ACCOUNTING PROCESS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF THE ORGANIZATIONS IN THE FIELD OF SERVICES

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Abstract

Purpose – *This paper aims to analyze the influence of the financial-accounting process on the performance of the organizations in the field of services*

Methodology/approach – *For this study, it was conducted a quantitative research, the sample of this study being represented by the employees from the professional service companies. The dimensions taken into account for describing the performance of the financial-accounting process were: time, quality, flexibility, budget, and level of importance.*

Findings – *The results indicated that the performance is given more by the quality of the financial-accounting operations and by the respect of the deadlines, as well as by the budget allocation for these operations*

Research limitations/implications – *This is an exploratory study, applied in professional service companies that are active in Romania*

Practical implications – *The results indicate that by increasing quality, ensuring lower costs in the financial and accounting areas, and respecting the deadlines, the performance of the company will increase. Also, improving the performance of the financial-accounting process directly contributes to improving organizational performance in the services field.*

Originality/value – *The authors analyzed the simple linear regression between the organizational performance and the performance values of the analyzed processes.*

Key words: *financial-accounting process, organizational performance, service performance,*

Introduction

Over the years, in the specialty literature, there have been several approaches to the concept of performance, this concept being important in any activity, but especially in the economic field. One of the most popular approaches to performance was conducted by Kaplan and Norton (1996), through their Balanced Scorecard matrix (Kaplan and Norton, 1996). When defining the customer perspective, Kaplan and Norton (1996) insisted from the beginning on some key issues that organizations need to focus on when it comes to customers or market segments: market share, customer retention, customer attraction, customer satisfaction, and customer profitability.

From the analysis of other concepts, like the profit-service chain (Heskett et al., 1994; Koys, 2001; Larivière, 2008; Coviello, Winklhofer, and Hamilton, 2006), we deduce other important indicators that describe the organizational performance: employee satisfaction level, level of employee loyalty, employee productivity, the quality level of the service, employee fluctuation, the level of customer satisfaction, customer retention rate, repeat rate of purchases, number of recommendations received from clients, company revenues, company profit.

Apart from the existing papers in the specialized literature, there were also developed some awards for quality and organizational excellence: Malcom Baldrige National Quality Award, Deming Award, European Quality Award (EFQM - European Foundation for Quality Management Award, 2013), and

The Romanian quality award J.M. Juran. In general, these awards analyze customer orientation, business results, employees, leadership, strategy, and processes.

Through this paper, the authors propose to analyze the relationship between the financial-accounting process and the performance of the service organizations. In this regard, a quantitative research was conducted, being analyzed the employees' perceptions. The paper focused on the situation existing in professional service companies that are active in Bucharest, Romania.

Literature review

Financial indicators were among the first used to measure the performance of an organization. They are easy to identify, define, measure, and improve (Hannabarger et al, 2007). However, just analyzing these indicators and improving them was not enough to describe the performance of companies. Thus, in 1992, Kaplan and Norton (1992) had the idea of building a "balanced dashboard", most commonly known as the Balanced Scorecard, where the financial perspective is just one of the main components that influence performance.

With the evolution of technology, the financial-accounting process has changed, this starting to be realized more and more with the help of computer programs. Cleary and Quinn (2016) studied the impact of cloud-based infrastructure in the field of accounting/finance on SMEs, as well as their performance in the enterprises analyzed. Their results indicated that the cloud-based accounting/finance infrastructure has a positive and statistically significant impact on organizational performance.

Analyzing various papers published in the financial field (Holler, 2009; Ebert et al., 2005; Kerzner, 2011; Okes, 2013; Militaru, 2015) scientific articles (Horváthová, E., 2010; Huang, 2010; Magness, 2006; Donker, Poff, and Zahir, 2008; Berrone, Surroca, and Tribó, 2007; Chang et al., 2016) it is found that there is there a great interest for this perspective and its relation with the organizational performance, but the results are presented in a general way, without being done concrete distinctions of these results for different categories of companies.

Thus, the authors wanted to test whether, in the case of the service providers in Bucharest, there is a positive direct relationship between the financial-accounting process and the organizational performance, the hypothesis to be tested being:

H1: Improving the performance of the financial-accounting process directly contributes to improving organizational performance in the services field.

Methodology

For this study, the authors used a questionnaire that was applied online for one month. The sample was represented by 150 employees working in the service companies in Bucharest, Romania. The largest share of respondents holds executive positions (81%), while the rest (19%) hold management positions within the analyzed service companies from Bucharest. The questionnaire measures the respondents' perception, the authors opting for a Likert scale measurement system with 5 response variants.

To define the organizational performance, the following variables were taken into account: profitability, revenue, market share, the perspective of clients, employees and interest groups, the process perspective, and the quality of services. Table 1 presents the variables chosen to determine the level of organizational performance, the codes of these variables, as well as the statements used to characterize these variables.

For the financial-accounting process, the analyzed performance had the following dimensions: time, flexibility, quality, cost (Barbu and Militaru, 2019), the statements that were used for describing them being presented in Table 2.

Table 1. The statements and variables associated with the organizational performance

Variable code	Variable	Statement
P	Profitability	I work in a profitable company.
R	Revenue	I work in a company with a high income.
M	Market share	The company has a good market share compared to its competitors.
Q	Service quality	The quality of the services offered by the company is high.
C	Clients	The clients are very satisfied with the goods and services provided by the company I work for.
E	Employees	I am generally satisfied with the job I have.
Pr	Processes	The usual processes in the organization I work for can / should be improved.
S	Stakeholders	The stakeholders were always satisfied with the performance of the company I work for.

Table 2. The statements and variables associated with the financial-accounting process

Variable code	Variable	Statement
P.L.P	Level of performance	In the company I work for, the financial-accounting process is performing.
P.L.I	Level of importance	In the company I work for, the financial-accounting process is very important.
P.T	Time	Financial-accounting operations are always performed on time.
P.F	Flexibility	The financial-accounting process is flexible in terms of changes that may occur in the operations performed.
P.Q	Quality	The quality of the financial-accounting services is very good.
P.C	Cost (Budget)	The activities carried out within the financial-accounting process aim at correctly establishing the budgets within the company, monitoring and carrying out corrective actions to respect these budgets.

Results

In the case of the financial-accounting process, the performance is given more by the quality of the financial-accounting operations and by the respect of the deadlines (the average being 4.21), as well as by the budget allocation for these operations (4.13), all of these results being presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The average of the notes associated with the dimensions of the performance in the case of the financial-accounting process

The note associated with the overall performance of the process was calculated according to Table 3, where its value is 4.13, which indicates a general level of agreement on the fact that in the analyzed companies providing services, the financial-accounting process is a performance one, with note 4.13 of 5.

Table 3. The calculation method of the financial accounting process performance

Variable	Calculation method	Value
Financial-Accounting process performance	$=(P.T+P.F+P.Q+P.C)/4$	4.13

Figure 2 shows the averages of the notes associated with the dimensions of the organizational performance, but also the general average of the performance of the studied organizations. Thus, it is found that the general average is 4.15 (the maximum being 5), the highest average being registered in the case of profitability (4.31). Also, the respondents considered that in general, the customers are satisfied with the services offered by the service providers (the average is 4.22). On the opposite side, the lowest average is recorded in the chapter of employees, where the average of these marks is 3.99.

Figure 2. The average of the notes associated with the dimensions of the organizational performance

The score associated with the organizational performance was calculated according to table 4, where its value is 4.15 out of the maximum of 5.

Table 4. The calculation method of organizational performance

New variable	Calculation method	Value
Performance	$=(P+ R+ M+ Q+ C+ E+ Pr+ S)/8$	4.15

In the case of the financial accounting process (Table 5), moderate positive correlations can be observed between the company performance and the quality of the financial-accounting operations ($R = 0.451$), respectively the performance of the company and the respect of the budget ($R = 0.531$), significant statistical correlations at a level of 99% confidence, this suggesting that with the increasing quality or ensuring lower costs in the financial and accounting areas, the performance of the company will also increase, this process being closely linked to the overall performance of the service company ($R = 0.558$, $p < 0.01$), which means that H1 is confirmed.

Also, in the case of this process, it is noted that the variable quality is closely related to the perception of the performance of the process, the Pearson coefficient being 0.697, which indicates a strong connection between the 2 mentioned variables, this connection being statistically significant at a degree of 99% confidence.

Table 5. Correlations between the financial-accounting process and organizational performance

	P.L.P	P.L.I	P.T	P.F	P.Q	P.C	Financial-Accounting process performance
P.I	.481**						
P.T	.554**	.474**					
P.F	.256**	.368**	.466**				
P.Q	.697**	.565**	.683**	.455**			
P.C	.424**	.475**	.452**	.254**	.475**		
Financial-Accounting process performance	.617**	.604**	.842**	.723**	.840**	.687**	
Organizational Performance	.515**	.401**	.385**	.373**	.451**	.531**	.558**

Next, the simple linear regression was analyzed, the dependent variable being the organizational performance, while the independent variable was represented by the performance values of the analyzed processes. Table 6 presents the summary of the models between the organizational performance (the dependent variable) and the performance of the analyzed processes (the independent variables).

Table 6. The relationship of performance with the financial accounting process

Model	The relationship of performance with the financial accounting process	R	R ²	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	Financial-Accounting process performance	0.558	0.312	0.307	0.477

In the case of the analyzed model, the value of the R2 determination coefficient is 0.312, which means that the variation of the dependent variable, that is, the organizational performance, is explained in a proportion of 31.2% of the independent variable, that is, the performance of the supply process. In Table 7, there are presented the coefficients of the analyzed model, where it can be seen that the value of Sig. is smaller than 0.05 which indicates that the coefficient is significant.

Table 7. Coefficients of the analyzed model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Confidence interval for B (95.0%)	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Inferior limit	Upper limit
(Constantă)	2.19	0.242		9.046	0	1.712	2.669
Financial-Accounting process performance	0.473	0.058	0.558	8.187	0	0.359	0.588

a. Dependent variable: Performance

The Pearson coefficient is 0.558 ($p < 0.05$), the two variables having a moderate, positive correlation, the equation of the regression line being:

$$Performance = 2.190 + 0.473 * \text{Financial Accounting process performance}$$

If we consider only the standardized coefficients, then for each increase with a unit of the independent variable, the dependent variable would register an increase of 0.558.

Conclusions and limits

By analyzing the financial-accounting process, the authors discovered that the performance of the analyzed process is influenced the most by the quality of the financial-accounting operations. Also, two more aspects need to be analyzed when we talk about process performance: time and budget. These results indicate that by increasing quality, ensuring lower costs in the financial and accounting areas, and respecting the deadlines, the performance of the company will increase. Also, improving the performance of the financial-accounting process directly contributes to improving the organizational performance in the services field ($R = 0.558$, $p < 0.01$), which means that H1 is confirmed.

When the notes associated with the dimensions of the organizational performance were analyzed, the authors discovered that the highest average note accorded by the respondents is in the case of profitability (4.31), which means that the employees considered that the company in which they work is largely profitable. On one hand, respondents believe that customers are satisfied with the service providers due to the high quality of the services. On the other hand, according to the employees' responses, their satisfaction about the workplace is a problem, which is why the service companies should give greater importance to this aspect, taking into account the fact that the human resource is one of the most important resources, which can directly affect the performance of the service provided.

This study also presents some limitations. Even though the sample was targeting the employees from the professional service company, the respondents surveyed worked in different fields. For example, 25 of them were working in the IT industry, 21 in Commerce, 19 in Financial and Banking, 14 in Construction, repairs, installation, 14 in the Transport sector, 11 in Consulting, the rest of them working in other sectors. If everyone worked in the same field, then the results might have been slightly different. Also, those results might have been different if all of the respondents had a management position, not just 19% of them.

Taking into account these data, this study can be considered an exploratory one. For future research, the authors will focus on a single domain of service activity, making separate studies on managers and the rest of the employees of the surveyed companies.

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